

(consistent with an E_a type of elimination reaction) and base catalysis would also have been observed.

Further, a good linear correlation of the rates of oxidation of the aliphatic alcohols by NBSA with the rate constants for the oxidation of similar systems by NBS⁸ underscores a formal similarity of the two transition states.

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Equilibrium Studies of Interaction of Oxovanadium(II), Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone, 4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin and 1-(2'-Furyl)-3-(4'-methyl-5'-hydroxycoumarin-6'-yl)propane-1,3-dione

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UNSATURATED lactones are well known for their selective inhibition of growth of plant and animal tissues, for toxicity in fish, antibacterial and haemorrhagic activity and for their effect on central nervous system. Coumarins belong to this class of compounds¹. It was, therefore, decided to investigate the interactions of coumarins with metal ions commonly present in the living systems and to study the effect of substitution of various ring systems on coumarin moiety. The following ligands were selected for the present study.

Experimental

The ligands 1, 2 and 3 were prepared by following the procedures reported earlier²⁻⁴. The metal ions were used in the form of their perchlorates, except for vanadium, where vanadyl sulphate was used. The concentrations of the metal ions were determined complexometrically⁵ by EDTA titrations. Dioxane was purified⁶. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration of the solution of known amount of the ligands (1, 1.023×10^{-3} ; 2, 1.005×10^{-3} ; 3, 1.006×10^{-3} M), known amounts of free HClO_4 (5.234×10^{-3} M), in the absence and presence of known amounts of the metal ions (VO^{II} , 1.187×10^{-3} ; Mn^{II} , 1.327×10^{-3} ; Co^{II} , 1.167×10^{-3} ; Ni^{II} , 1.062×10^{-3} ; Cu^{II} , 9.704×10^{-3} M) with sodium hydroxide solution (2.469×10^{-1} M) at 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

The $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁷. The results are stated in Table 1. The pK value of phenol in 50 : 50 (v/v) water-dioxane system was 12.0. In *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in spite of the electron withdrawing CH_3CO group, the value was found to be 12.06, probably due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding. The acidities of the coumarin and the diketone derivatives were comparatively higher than that of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone because of the electron withdrawing oxygen atoms attached to adjacent rings. Weak hydrogen bonding in the diketone derivative lowers its acidity to some extent.

With the exception of the VO^{II} complexes of acetophenone and diketone derivatives, the difference ($\log K_1 - \log K_2$) was less than 1.78, suggesting the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes by simultaneous equilibria⁸. In the VO^{II} complexes of the acetophenone and diketone derivatives, the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were formed in stepwise manner. VO^{II} and Cu^{II} were found to form more stable complexes with all the three ligands (Table 1). Higher stability of these complexes could be attributed to the Jahn-Teller distortion⁹. The $\log K_A$ value of Cu^{II} complex of the

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS*

Cations	Ligands					
	1		2		3	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
H ⁺	12.06	—	9.85	—	10.25	—
VO ²⁺	11.34	8.59	9.77	9.24	9.88	7.76
Mn ²⁺	6.22	5.88	4.68	4.12	5.00	4.24
Co ²⁺	6.86	6.43	5.25	4.57	5.15	5.07
Ni ²⁺	6.65	5.71	5.95	4.91	5.18	4.74
Cu ²⁺	8.64	7.92	7.75	—	6.90	6.48

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂, respectively.

coumarin derivative could not be evaluated due to the commencement of precipitation at pH ≈ 4.7. With the exception of Mn^{II} complexes, the log K₁ values of the diketone complexes were slightly less than those of the acetophenone and coumarin derivatives. This was probably due to the bigger size of the diketone molecule which caused steric hindrance in the complex formation process.

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Potentiometric and Biocidal Studies of Ternary Complexes of some Transition Metals with *N*-Pyridylanthranilic Acid (NPA) and some Bidentate Ligands

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A survey of the literature reveals the description of chelates of a number of bivalent metals/lanthanide^{1,2} ions with anthranilic acid. The synthesis and chelating behaviour of *N*-phenylanthranilic acid have been investigated by Harris and Sweet³.

In this communication, the synthesis of a new ligand, *N*-pyridylanthranilic acid (NPA) from 2-aminopyridine and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid has been described and its proton dissociation constant (NPA, $pK_1 = 3.46 \pm 0.04$; IMDA, $pK_1 = 3.11 \pm 0.09$, $pK_2 = 9.45 \pm 0.11$) were determined by the method of Chaberck and Martell⁴. The binary and ternary complex formation of some bivalent metals with the synthesised ligand and a number of bidentate ligands have been studied potentiometrically, and the values of formation constants of the resulting complexes, evaluated by the respective methods of Thompson and Loraas⁵ and Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁶, are recorded.

The insoluble ternary complex, 1:1:1 Cu^{II}-NPA-HQ has also been isolated and characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The biocidal activity of metal ions, the ligands, and the Cu^{II} complex towards some selected fungi and bacteria are evaluated (Table 3).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of BDH or E. Merck grade unless stated otherwise. The metal

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